

Polarographic Study of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Copper(II) with Diamines and Amino Acids

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Schaap and McMasters¹ studied mixed-ligand complexes of Cu^{II} with ethylenediamine and oxalate ion. Sundaresan and Sundaram² reported polarographic study of mixed complexes of Cu^{II} with glycine and α -alanine. Later, Saxena *et al.*³ made polarographic study of mixed complexes of Cu^{II} with pyridoxine and some amino acids and reported that in each case a single mixed species (1 : 1 : 1) is formed. Alaejos *et al.*⁴ reported polarographic study of mixed system Cu^{II}-glycine-isoleucine and concluded that only a single mixed species [Cu(gly)(isole)] is formed.

From the survey of literature it appears that no polarographic study has been reported so far in regard to the mixed-ligand complexes of Cu^{II} with diamines and aminoacids. Hence, the title study has been undertaken on the mixed-ligand systems involving ethylenediamine and propylenediamine as the primary ligands and some amino acids, viz. glycine, DL-alanine, DL-valine and L-isoleucine as the secondary ligands.

Results and Discussion

Cu^{II} gives well-defined waves (typical plots in Fig. 1) in the presence of increasing concentrations of ethylenediamine (en), propylenediamine (pn), glycine (gly), DL-alanine (ala), DL-valine (val) and L-isoleucine (isole). This is true for both the simple and mixed systems. The plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}_{corr}$ are linear and pass through the origin, confirming the diffusion-controlled nature of the waves. The slope values of linear plots of $\log i/(i_d-i)$ vs $E_{d,e}$ lie in the range 30–32 mV (at 25°), thereby showing⁵ the reversible nature of Cu^{II} in the presence of single as well as mixed-ligands under study.

Free-ligand concentrations were calculated from the

pK_a values (Table 1) of the ligands and pH of the solution. The stability constants of simple complexes of Cu^{II} with ethylenediamine, propylenediamine and above mentioned amino acids were determined separately prior to the study of mixed-ligand systems. Identical conditions were maintained in both the simple and mixed systems. Representative data in respect of Cu^{II}-ethylenediamine system are presented in Table 2.

Fig. 1. C.V. curves of Cu^{II}-ethylenediamine system; curves 1–8 correspond to $[en]_1 = 0.00, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08$ and $0.10 M$ respectively.

TABLE I— pK_a VALUES OF THE LIGANDS

Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 1.0 M$ (NaNO₃)

Sl. no.	Ligand	pK_a	
		pK_1	pK_2
1.	Ethylenediamine (en)	7.05	10.10
2.	Propylenediamine (pn)	7.00	9.80
3.	Glycine (gly)	2.36	9.78
4.	DL-alanine (ala)	2.10	9.87
5.	DL-valine (val)	2.32	9.72
6.	L-isoleucine (isole)	2.50	9.75

TABLE 2-POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{ij}[X]$ FUNCTIONS FOR Cu^{II} -ETHYLENEDIAMINE SYSTEM

$[Cu^{II}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 1.0 M$ (NaNO₃), pH = 6.60, temp. = 25 ± 0 °C, [Triton X-100] = 2.0 × 10⁻³%, $(E_{1/2})_s^* = +0.018 V$ (S.C.E.), $i_d = 8.06 \mu A$

$[en]_i^{**}$ M	$[en]_f^{**}$ 10 ⁶ M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V	Slope mV	$F_0[X]$ 10 ⁻⁸	$F_1[X]$ 10 ⁻¹⁴	$F_2[X]$ 10 ⁻²⁰
(S.C.E.)							
0.01	1.1	7.92	0.242	30	6.42	5.77	-
0.02	2.2	7.77	0.255	30	18.04	8.05	2.90
0.03	3.4	7.52	0.264	31	37.59	11.19	2.84
0.04	4.5	7.52	0.271	31	64.88	14.48	2.90
0.06	6.7	7.42	0.281	32	143.34	21.29	2.92
0.08	9.0	7.30	0.287	32	251.43	28.03	2.94
0.10	11.2	7.02	0.293	33	386.05	34.44	2.93

* = $E_{1/2}$ of simple Cu^{II} ion.

$[en]_i$ = Total (analytical) concentration of ethylenediamine (en);

$[en]_f$ = free ligand concentration of ethylenediamine (en).

The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs log [en], log [pn], log [gly] and log [ala] are smooth curves. This shows the formation of successive complexes. Their composition and stability constants have been determined by DeFord and Hume's method⁶. However, in the case of Cu^{II} -valine and Cu^{II} -isoleucine systems, the plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs log [val⁻] and log [isole⁻] are straight-lines thereby showing the formation of a single complex in

TABLE 3-COMPOSITION AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SIMPLE COMPLEXES OF Cu^{II} WITH DIAMINES AND AMINO ACIDS

System	Complex species	Stability constant
Cu^{II} -en	$[Cu(en)]^{2+}$	log $\beta_1 = 14.20$
	$[Cu(en)_2]^{2+}$	log $\beta_2 = 20.46$
Cu^{II} -pn	$[Cu(pn)]^{2+}$	log $\beta_1 = 14.60$
	$[Cu(pn)_2]^{2+}$	log $\beta_2 = 20.32$
Cu^{II} -gly	$[Cu(gly)]^+$	log $\beta_1 = 12.27$
	$[Cu(gly)_2]$	log $\beta_2 = 15.54$
Cu^{II} -ala	$[Cu(ala)]^+$	log $\beta_1 = 12.25$
	$[Cu(ala)_2]$	log $\beta_2 = 15.43$
Cu^{II} -val	$[Cu(val)_2]$	log $\beta_2 = 15.45$
Cu^{II} -isole	$[Cu(isole)_2]$	log $\beta_2 = 15.48$

each of these systems. The composition and stability constants of these complexes have been determined by Lingane's method⁷. The composition and stability constants of simple complexes are presented in Table 3.

Mixed complexes : The concentrations of diamines was varied from 0 to 0.10 M keeping the concentration of amino acid constant at 0.10 M. The $E_{1/2}$ values were more negative than those obtained in the absence of amino acid, thereby showing the formation of mixed complexes. The system was repeated at another concentration (0.20 M) of the amino acid. The composition and stability constants of mixed complexes were determined by Schaap and McMasters method¹. The polarographic characteristics and $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ functions (X = en or pn; Y = gly or ala or val or isole) were determined and these are presented for a typical mixed system Cu^{II} -ethylenediamine-glycine, in Table 4. From the intercept of the plots of $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ vs [en] or [pn] the values of constants¹ A, B and C were obtained. An analysis of the values of these constants shows that only one mixed complex species is formed in each case. The composition and stability constants of mixed-ligand systems are presented in Table 5.

The stability constant of the mixed complex which characterises the following equilibrium (charges omitted),

is given by

$$\beta_{ij} = \frac{[MX_iY_j]}{[M][X]^i[Y]^j} \quad (2)$$

The mixing constant (K_M) correlates the stability of the mixed complex species to that of the parent complexes and can be defined² as the equilibrium constant of the reaction,

by the expression

$$K_M = \frac{[MX_iY_j]}{[MX_m]^{i/m}[MY_m]^{j/m}} \quad (4)$$

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ FUNCTIONS FOR Cu^{II} -ETHYLENEDIAMINE-GLYCINE SYSTEM
 $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3), $\text{pH} = 6.60$, $\text{temp.} = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $[\text{Triton X-100}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$, $(E_{1/2})_s = +0.018 \text{ V}$ (S.C.E.)

$[\text{en}]_t$ M	$[\text{en}]_t$ $10^6 M$	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	$F_{\infty}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-9}$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ 10^{-14}	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ 10^{-20}
Series I [gly] = 0.1 M (fixed)							
0.01	1.1	7.90	0.258	30	2.24	—	—
0.02	2.2	7.86	0.267	31	4.54	11.36	2.61
0.03	3.4	7.82	0.273	32	7.29	15.75	3.04
0.04	4.5	7.82	0.278	32	10.76	19.56	3.13
0.06	6.7	7.67	0.285	32	18.94	25.17	2.92
0.08	9.0	7.55	0.291	33	30.71	32.00	2.98
0.10	11.2	7.53	0.296	33	45.47	38.77	3.00
Series II [gly] = 0.2 M (fixed)							
0.01	1.1	7.88	0.260	31	2.63	—	—
0.02	2.2	7.76	0.270	32	5.81	12.57	2.70
0.03	3.4	7.70	0.275	32	8.65	16.82	3.10
0.04	4.5	7.56	0.279	33	12.04	20.18	3.06
0.06	6.7	7.53	0.286	33	20.85	26.53	3.00
0.08	9.0	7.46	0.292	32	33.59	23.11	3.10
0.10	11.2	7.46	0.297	33	49.61	41.47	3.12

TABLE 5—VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANT, MIXING CONSTANT AND STABILISATION CONSTANT FOR MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Cu^{II}

Mixed species	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log K_M$	$\log K_s$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{gly})]^+$	18.42	+0.42	+0.12
$[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{ala})]^+$	18.66	+0.71	+0.41
$[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{val})]^+$	18.40	+0.44	+0.14
$[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{isole})]^+$	18.38	+0.41	+0.11
$[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})(\text{gly})]^+$	18.48	+0.55	+0.25
$[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})(\text{ala})]^+$	18.74	+0.86	+0.56
$[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})(\text{val})]^+$	18.59	+0.70	+0.40
$[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})(\text{isole})]^+$	18.62	+0.72	+0.42

$$\text{or } K_M = \beta_{ij} \beta_{\text{mo}}^{-i/m} \beta_{\text{om}}^{-j/m} \quad (5)$$

It is obvious² that a major contribution to K_M will arise from statistical factors. Hence, Marcus and Elizer⁸ defined another parameter called the 'stabilisation constant' which for ligands of equal denticity is given by

$$\log K_s = \log K_M - \log \left(\frac{n!}{i! j!} \right) \quad (6)$$

where, $n = i + j$. The stabilisation constant, therefore, gives a measure of the extra stability of mixed complex due to electrostatic forces, geometric forces, solvent effect etc., in addition to the statistical effect.

The values of K_M and K_s have been calculated from equations (5) and (6) respectively, and are listed in Table 5. A perusal of Table 5 shows that the log values of K_M and K_s are positive showing that mixed complexes are relatively more stable than the binary complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their stock solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The concentration of Cu^{II} was maintained constant at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. Polarograms of the deaerated solutions were obtained using a Toshniwal CL 02 B polarograph at a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3) and $\text{pH} = 6.6$ in the presence of Triton X-100 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$) at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The d.m.c. had the following characteristics (in 1.0 M NaNO_3 , open circuit): $m = 2.40 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 3.10 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.16 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$, $h_{\text{corr}} = 52.4 \text{ cm}$.

The pK_a values of the ligands were determined by the titration method⁹ using glass electrode. The values obtained at 25° and $\mu = 1.0 M$ ($NaNO_3$) compared fairly well with the literature values¹⁰.

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